

Valorization of orange peels as a source of natural antioxidants from pectin-extracted compounds

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Abstract

Citrus peels, a major by-product of the fruit industry, are rich in pectic polysaccharides with potential bioactive properties. This study aimed to extract and characterize pectin from orange peels and to evaluate its physicochemical properties and antioxidant potential. The extracted pectin was analyzed for its physicochemical characteristics, and its antioxidant potential was assessed using three *in vitro* assays: DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP. The extraction yielded 19.0% dry material, with moisture (13.0%), ash (10.3%), total sugars (16.3%), and protein content (0.10%). Phytochemical analysis showed low levels of polyphenols (1.17 mg GAE/g DM), flavonoids (0.55 mg QE/g DM), and condensed tannins (0.10 mg CE/g DM). Despite these low phenolic contents, the pectic extract exhibited significant antioxidant activity in DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP assays, with IC₅₀ values of 2.32, 2.00, and 1.85 mg/mL, respectively. These findings indicate that orange peel pectin is a promising natural antioxidant source with potential applications in the food, nutraceutical, and pharmaceutical industries, promoting the sustainable valorization of citrus by-products.

Keywords: Orange peel, Pectin, Extraction, Antioxidant activity, DPPH, ABTS, Citrus by-products

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INTRODUCTION

Citrus fruits represent one of the most important fruit crops worldwide, with an estimated annual global production exceeding 115 million tons (Gonzatto and Santos, 2023). Among them, oranges are the most widely consumed due to their pleasant flavor, high nutritional value, and richness in bioactive compounds - over 170 phytochemicals have been identified (Ahmad and Langrish, 2012; Wang *et al.*, 2007). Oranges are typically consumed fresh, or processed into marmalades and juices (Carmona *et al.*, 2012).

In Tunisia, citrus cultivation is a major agro-economic activity, particularly concentrated in the Cap Bon region, which accounts for most of the country's production (Ministère de l'Agriculture de Tunisie, 2014).

Orange peels are an abundant by-product of juice and marmalade industries and contain numerous nutritional and functional components, including water, proteins, sugars, minerals, essential oils, fibers, carotenoids, vitamin C, and phenolic compounds. The most common route of industrial valorization involves the extraction of essential oils, which serve as natural alternatives to synthetic fungicides (Singh *et al.*, 2010; Fisher and Phillips, 2006). These oils are also employed in functional food formulations and in the confectionery industry (candies, jams, etc.) through direct incorporation of orange peel material (Bocco *et al.*, 1998).

Moreover, citrus peels are increasingly used as feedstock and for biofuel and biogas production (Wilkins *et al.*, 2007; Pourbafrani *et al.*, 2010), as well as for the manufacture of biodegradable plastics (Byrne *et al.*, 2004) and as corrosion inhibitors for metals and alloys (Da Rocha *et al.*, 2010).

Citrus peels are particularly rich in dietary fibers (mainly pectin) and phenolic compounds, notably flavonoids and phenolic acids, which exhibit a broad spectrum of

biological activities, including antioxidant, therapeutic, antiviral, antifungal, and antibacterial effects (Ma *et al.*, 2009; Huang and Ho, 2010).

The extraction of pectin from orange peels has attracted growing scientific interest because pectin acts as a natural antioxidant and a valuable co-product derived from apple pomace and citrus peel residues. Pectin is widely used in the food industry as an emulsifier, stabilizer, and gelling agent. The global demand for pectin exceeds 30,000 tons per year and continues to grow at a rate of 4–5 % annually (Yeoh *et al.*, 2008).

Recent studies have explored alternative fruit sources such as apricots, dates, and figs for pectin extraction, motivated by their abundance and local availability. From both economic and environmental perspectives, the valorization of such agro-industrial by-products into useful co-products like pectin represents a sustainable strategy for the food industry.

A major interest in pectic oligosaccharides (POS) lies in their structural diversity, which enables a wide range of functional and pharmacological applications. The development of pectin-derived oligosaccharides with prebiotic or pharmaceutical properties constitutes an emerging research area. These compounds have been associated with protective effects against colon cancer, antibacterial activity, suppression of hepatic lipid accumulation, inhibition of bacterial adhesion to epithelial cells, and stimulation of beneficial gut microbiota such as *Bifidobacterium* and *Eubacterium rectale* (Qiang *et al.*, 2009; Manderson *et al.*, 2005).

Accordingly, the present study was devoted to the extraction and physicochemical characterization of pectin from orange peels (PEOP), followed by the evaluation of its *in vitro* antioxidant potential using DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP assays.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents

Folin–Ciocalteu, Ethanol, sodium carbonate, DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) ABTS (2,2'-azino-bis-3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid, methanol, ethanol, epinephrine, NaCl, hydrochloric acid (HCl), and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were purchased from sigma-Aldrich Co., Munich (Germany). All the other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of orange peel powder

A single batch of “Maltaise demi-sanguine” oranges was collected in March 2019 through an agronomist from the Menzel Bouzalfa region. The harvested fruits were at commercial maturity, exhibiting an orange color and an average weight of 185 ± 7.07 g. Upon arrival at the laboratory, the oranges were washed with tap water, and the peels were carefully separated from the fresh fruits. The fresh peels were oven-dried at 50 °C for three days, finely ground using an electric blender, and sieved to obtain a uniform powder. The resulting powder was stored in tightly sealed, dark-labeled containers at room temperature until further use for pectin extraction.

Extraction of pectin

Most soluble pectin from fruits is released into the juice during processing. The extraction process aims to solubilize the remaining pectins in the peel using a diluted acid under heat. The main steps of the extraction procedure were as follows:

- Preparation of raw material and solubilization of protopectin.
- Alcoholic precipitation of pectin.
- Washing, drying, and conditioning of the extracted pectin.

Pectins were extracted from the orange peel cell wall material using diluted hydrochloric acid (HCl). The extraction conditions (pH, temperature, and duration) were optimized to achieve the highest possible yield.

Orange peels were separated and oven-dried at 50 °C for three days, then ground using a blender, and the resulting powder was stored at room temperature (25 °C). For extraction, 10 g of peel powder were mixed with 495.8 mL of distilled water and 4.2 mL of HCl, adjusting the pH to 3. The mixture was stirred and heated at 100 °C for 10 min, then cooled to room temperature. The suspension was centrifuged at $5000 \times g$ for 20 min, and the supernatant was collected and adjusted to pH 7. Absolute ethanol (twice the supernatant volume) was then added under gentle stirring for 5 min at room temperature, followed by incubation for 12 h to allow pectin precipitation. The precipitate recovered by centrifugation, washed with 96% ethanol, and oven-dried at 40 °C until a constant weight was obtained. The dried pectin was finally dissolved in water to prepare the pectic extract of orange peels (PEOP) for further analyses.

Physicochemical characterization

Yield

After extraction, the wet pectin was dried at 40 °C to a constant weight, cooled in a desiccator, and weighed. The yield (%) was calculated relative to the dry weight of the raw material using the following formula:

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of dried pectin}}{\text{Weight of dry peel powder}} \times 100$$

The moisture content and dry matter content were determined according to standard gravimetric methods.

Ash and organic matter content

The ash content and organic matter content (MO) were determined following the AOAC (1990) method. One gram of the dry powder was placed in a pre-weighed porcelain crucible and incinerated in a muffle furnace at 550 °C for 3 h. The loss in weight corresponds to organic matter, while the residue represents the mineral (ash) content (Cunniff and Washington, 1997).

$$\text{MO (\%)} = \frac{PI - PF}{PE} \times 100 \text{ and } \text{MM (\%)} = \frac{PF - \text{Weight of crucible}}{PE} \times 100$$

where:

PI = initial weight (crucible + sample before incineration),

PF = final weight (crucible + ash),

PE = weight of the sample.

Determination of Total Polyphenols

The total phenolic content (TPC) was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu method as modified by Singleton *et al.* (1988). Briefly, 25 μL of extract were mixed with 2.125 mL of Folin–Ciocalteu reagent and 2 mL of distilled water. After vortexing, the mixture was left to stand for 3 min, then 375 μL of 10% sodium carbonate was added. The reaction mixture was incubated in a water bath at 37 °C for 2 h. The absorbance was measured at 760 nm using a spectrophotometer (Singleton, 1999).

The TPC was calculated from a calibration curve prepared with gallic acid and expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent per g of dry matter (mg GAE/g DM).

Determination of total flavonoids

Total flavonoid content (TFC) was determined according to the method of Zhishen *et al.*. Briefly, 0.5 mL of PEOP was mixed with 120 μL of 5% NaNO_2 . After 5 min, 120 μL of 10% AlCl_3 and 800 μL of 1 M NaOH were added. The absorbance was recorded at 510 nm. The TFC was calculated from a calibration curve using quercetin as a standard and expressed as mg quercetin equivalent per g of dry matter (mg QE/g DM) (Zhishen *et al.*, 1999).

Determination of condensed tannins

Condensed tannins were quantified using the vanillin–HCl method described by Price *et al.* (1978). In an acidic medium, vanillin reacts with condensed tannin units to form a red complex measured at 550 nm. Quantification was performed using a catechin calibration curve, and results were expressed as mg catechin equivalent per g of dry matter (mg CE/g DM) (Price *et al.*, 1978).

Protein content

Protein concentration was determined by the Bradford method (Bradford, 1976), which is based on the binding of Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye to proteins, causing a shift in absorbance maximum from 465 to 595 nm. The absorbance was measured at 595 nm, and the protein content was calculated using a bovine serum albumin (BSA) standard curve.

Total sugar content

Total neutral monosaccharides were estimated calorimetrically according to Dubois *et al.* (1956). One milliliter of extract was mixed with 50 μ L of 75% phenol, followed by rapid addition of 2.5 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid. The mixture was kept at room temperature in the dark for 30 min, and the absorbance was measured at 485 nm. Total sugars were quantified using a glucose calibration curve and expressed as mg glucose equivalent per g of dry matter (mg GE/g DM) (DuBois *et al.*, 1956).

Antioxidant activity

The antioxidant potential of the extracted pectin was evaluated using three complementary *in vitro* assays: the DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging test, the ABTS (2,2'-azino-bis-3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) assay, and the FRAP (Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power) assay.

ABTS radical cation scavenging assay

The ABTS assay was performed according to Siddhuraju and Becker (2006). An ABTS solution (7 mM) was mixed with 2.45 mM potassium persulfate and incubated in the dark for 16 h at room temperature to generate the ABTS^{•+} radical cation. The solution was diluted to an absorbance of 0.70 ± 0.02 at 734 nm. Then, 1 mL of PEOP (at various concentrations) was mixed with 3 mL of ABTS^{•+} solution and incubated in the dark for 60 min (Siddhuraju 2006). Absorbance was measured at 734 nm, and the percentage inhibition was calculated as:

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \frac{A_0 - A_s}{A_0} \times 100$$

where A_0 is the absorbance of the control and A_s is the absorbance of the sample.

DPPH radical scavenging assay

The DPPH assay was performed following Gorinstein *et al.* (2004). A mixture of 200 μ L of different concentration of PEOP and 2.8 mL of methanolic DPPH solution (0.1 mM) was shaken vigorously for 30 s and incubated in the

dark at room temperature for 30 min. The absorbance was measured at 517 nm, and the percentage inhibition of DPPH radicals was calculated using the same formula as above (Gorinstein *et al.*, 2004).

FRAP assay

In this study, the FRAP assay was performed following the method of Chokri *et al.* (2024), with slight modifications. The reaction mixture consisted of 1.25 mL of 0.2 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.6), 1.25 mL of 1% potassium ferricyanide [$K_3Fe(CN)_6$], and 1 mL of pectin extract (PEOP) at various concentrations (ranging from 2 to 60 μ M). The mixture was incubated at 50 °C for 20 min to allow the reduction of ferricyanide to ferrocyanide. After incubation, 1.25 mL of 10% trichloroacetic acid was added to stop the reaction, and the mixture was centrifuged (Eppendorf centrifuge, Hamburg, Germany) at 4000 rpm for 10 min to remove any precipitate. An aliquot of the supernatant (1.25 mL) was then combined with 1.25 mL of distilled water and 0.25 mL of freshly prepared 0.2% ferric chloride ($FeCl_3$). The resulting solution was incubated in the dark for 10 min, and absorbance was measured at 700 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Techcomp S1020). This assay evaluates the formation of a ferric ion complex (Prussian blue), where higher absorbance values indicate greater reducing power of the pectin extract (Chokri *et al.*, 2024).

RESULTS

Phytochemical study

Physicochemical characterization

The evaluation of several physicochemical parameters of the Extracted Pectic Extract from Orange Peels (PEOP) revealed the following results: yield 19%, moisture content 13%, ash content 10.32%, organic matter 89.86%, dry matter 87%, protein content 0.1%, and total sugars 16.26% (Table 1).

Phenolic composition analysis

The phytochemical screening (Table 2) showed that the pectic extract from orange peels contained low amounts of total polyphenols, flavonoids, and condensed tannins.

In vitro antioxidant activity evaluation

The antioxidant activity of the pectic extract of orange peel (PEOP) was evaluated using three complementary assays: DPPH radical scavenging, ABTS radical scavenging, and reducing power tests.

Table 1: Physicochemical composition of the pectic extract from orange peels (PEOP)

Extract	Yield (%)	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	Organics Matter (%)	Dry Matter (%)	Proteins (%)	Total sugars (%)
PEOP	19	13.0 \pm 0.23	10.3 \pm 0.27	89.9 \pm 0.23	87.0 \pm 0.23	0.10 \pm 0.003	16.3 \pm 0.25

Table 2: Phenolic compound analysis of the pectic extract from orange peels (PEOP)

Total polyphenols ^a	Total flavonoids ^b	Condensed tannins ^c
1.17 \pm 0.21	0.55 \pm 0.05	0.10 \pm 0.03

^a Expressed as mg gallic acid equivalents per g dry matter (mg GAE/g DM), ^b Expressed as mg quercetin equivalents per g dry matter (mg QE/g DM), ^c Expressed as mg catechin equivalents per g dry matter (mg CE/g DM).

DPPH radical scavenging activity

As shown in the first graph (Figure 1A), the DPPH inhibition percentage of PEOP increased in a concentration-dependent manner, indicating that its free radical scavenging capacity rises with higher concentrations. However, ascorbic acid (vitamin C) exhibited stronger activity across all tested concentrations. At the highest concentration (5 mg/mL), PEOP achieved approximately 80–85% inhibition, compared to nearly 95–100% for ascorbic acid. PEOP possesses a notable ability to neutralize DPPH radicals, though it remains slightly less potent than the standard antioxidant, ascorbic acid.

Figure 1: Antioxidant activity of the pectic extract of orange peel (PEOP) evaluated by (A) DPPH radical scavenging assay, (B) ABTS radical scavenging assay, and (C) reducing power assay compared with standard antioxidants (ascorbic acid and BHA)

Table 3: Comparison of IC₅₀ values for PEOP and ascorbic acid in DPPH and ABTS assays

Samples	DPPH (mg/mL)	ABTS (mg/mL)
PEOP	2.32 ± 0.27	2.00 ± 0.3
Ascorbic acid	1.20 ± 0.02	1.10 ± 0.03

ABTS radical scavenging activity

The ABTS inhibition graph (Figure 1B) also shows a dose-dependent increase for both PEOP and ascorbic acid. The scavenging activity of PEOP is comparable to that of ascorbic acid, especially at higher concentrations (3–4 mg/mL), where both exceed 80% inhibition. The pectic extract displays a strong ABTS radical scavenging capacity, suggesting the presence of bioactive compounds capable of donating electrons or hydrogen atoms to stabilize free radicals. The calculated half maximal inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀) were 2.32 mg/mL for DPPH and 2.00 mg/mL for ABTS. A lower IC₅₀ value indicates a higher antioxidant capacity. The pectic extract exhibited strong antioxidant potential, with IC₅₀ values comparable to those of ascorbic acid, used as the reference compound (Table 3).

Reducing power (OD 700 nm)

In the reducing power assay (Figure 1C), PEOP demonstrated an increasing absorbance with concentration, confirming its ability to reduce ferric (Fe³⁺) to ferrous (Fe²⁺) ions. However, its reducing potential was lower than that of BHA (Butylated Hydroxyanisole), a synthetic antioxidant. Although PEOP shows moderate reducing power compared to BHA, it still indicates effective electron-donating capacity, reinforcing its antioxidant potential.

DISCUSSION

The fruit peel, or pericarp, consists of two layers: the outer epicarp (flavedo or zest), brightly colored due to flavonoids, and the inner mesocarp (albedo), which is white and spongy (Rana *et al.*, 2023). Citrus peel composition varies with variety, climate, and environment. Pectins, plant-derived polysaccharides abundant in fruit cell walls, are industrially extracted from citrus peels and apple pomace and represent valuable bioactive compounds (Voragen *et al.*, 1995).

In the present study, we first demonstrated that the pectic extraction yield was approximately 19%. However, this yield varies among different fruits and depends on the extraction conditions such as pH, temperature, duration, and the type of acid used for solubilization (Yapo and Koffi, 2006; Faravash and Ashtiani, 2008).

Regarding the physicochemical characterization, our results showed that the moisture and total sugar contents were consistent with the values established by FAO/WHO standards, indicating acceptable levels for good stability during storage. Conversely, the ash content of PEOP was about 10.3%, a value close to that reported by Delluca and Joslyn (1957), who found that the ash content of pectin precipitated by mineral salts ranges between 8 and 25%. These levels increase with the pH of precipitation and the concentration of hydrochloric acid, whereas the use of organic solvents such as ethanol tends to reduce ash content by enhancing the removal of impurities during pectin precipitation. According to Cheftel, mineral salts are co-precipitated with pectin when precipitation occurs in alcohol concentrations of 50–60% (Cheftel, 1980).

However, Nithish *et al.* obtained lower ash contents in pectin precipitated from lemon peels using aluminum chloride (Nithish *et al.*, 2025).

Li *et al.* (2007) reported that orange peels exhibit a notable affinity for metal ions such as Ni, Cu, Pb, Zn, and Co, suggesting potential non-food applications, particularly the use of pectins as heavy metal chelating agents in wastewater treatment.

The dry matter, organic matter, and mineral matter contents were 87.0%, 89.9 %, and 10.3%, respectively. These values may reflect the climatic conditions of the sampling area (North-East Tunisia), a mild and humid region characterized by high rainfall (Rejeb *et al.*, 1993).

Our results also revealed that the protein content of the extracted orange peel pectin was within the acceptable limits established by Herbsthier and Fox, who reported a maximum protein level of 2.5% for high-quality pectin. The low protein values observed in our extract are probably due to partial hydrolysis by HCl (pH 3) during solubilization (Herbstreith and Fox, 2006). This hydrolysis depends directly on the type of acid used. Legentil *et al.* demonstrated that HCl is more effective in protein hydrolysis compared to cyclohexane-trans-1,2-diaminetetra-acetate (CDTA) (Legentil *et al.* 1995).

According to Yapo and Koffi, solubilization of pectin using acids such as citric acid may lead to co-solubilization of proteins, with protein levels ranging between 1.4 and 5.1%, compared to 0.9% for pectin solubilized in oxalate or water (Yapo and Koffi, 2006). These proteins are associated with pectins through arabinogalactan linkages (Seymour and Knox, 2002).

The total sugar content of our orange peel pectin (16.3%) was also close to the standard value (16.0%) reported by LEU and FAO/WHO (cited by Herbstreith and Fox, 2006).

Numerous studies have confirmed that cell wall polysaccharides, particularly pectins, exhibit qualitative and quantitative variations depending on factors such as fruit variety, maturity stage, geographic origin, and storage conditions (Kurz *et al.*, 2008). Kurz *et al.* further noted that pectins are more affected by fruit ripening than other polysaccharides like cellulose and hemicellulose, which remain relatively stable. According to Rous and Crandall, purer pectins have high galacturonic acid content and low ash content (Rouse and Crandall, 1978), while Levinge *et al.* (2002) reported values ranging from 29.0 to 52.8%.

The analysis of total polyphenols, flavonoids, and tannins in our extract revealed low concentrations of 1.17 mg GAE/g DM, 0.55 mg QE/g DM, and 0.1 mg CE/g DM, respectively. Similar findings have been reported by Ralet *et al.*, and Yapo *et al.*, who observed phenolic acid contents between 0.1 and 0.7%, gradually reduced through successive alcohol washings at different concentrations (Ralet *et al.*, 2005; Yapo *et al.*, 2007).

Moreover, Kurz *et al.* demonstrated that the polyphenolic composition of fruits varies both qualitatively and quantitatively depending on the fruit species, variety, maturity stage, geographical origin, and storage conditions of the raw material (Kurz *et al.* 2008).

Finally, the antioxidant activity of the pectic extract of orange peel (PEOP) was evaluated using DPPH, ABTS, and reducing power assays, and the results showed a clear concentration-dependent increase in activity across all tests (Figure 1). In the DPPH assay, PEOP exhibited a strong radical scavenging effect, reaching nearly 80% inhibition at 5 mg/mL, although slightly lower than ascorbic acid. Similarly, in the ABTS assay, PEOP demonstrated comparable scavenging activity to ascorbic acid at higher concentrations, confirming its efficiency in neutralizing free radicals. The reducing power of PEOP also increased with concentration but remained lower than that of BHA, indicating a moderate electron-donating ability. Overall, these results highlight that PEOP possesses significant antioxidant potential due to its richness in bioactive compounds such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and pectic polysaccharides, making it a promising natural source of antioxidants for food and pharmaceutical applications.

The evaluation of the antioxidant capacity of the orange peel pectic extract against DPPH and ABTS radicals revealed a significant activity, with IC₅₀ values of 2.32 and 2 mg/mL, respectively. This richness in polysaccharides and antioxidant power suggests that pectin contributes to nutritional balance and promotes optimal physiological function. The presence of high sugar levels, mainly sucrose, is known to facilitate intestinal transit and improve bowel function (Rtibi *et al.*, 2016; 2017), emphasizing the therapeutic relevance of these pectic compounds in the digestive system. Additionally, the hydroxyl groups in pectin molecules contribute to their antioxidant capacity. In fact, pectic polysaccharides from apple, commercial pectin, and citrus peel pectin have been shown to exhibit strong antioxidant activity (Wang and Lü, 2014; Wang *et al.*, 2014).

CONCLUSION

Orange peel pectin was successfully extracted with a yield of 19% and displayed favorable physicochemical properties. Although it contained low amounts of polyphenols, flavonoids, and tannins, the extract exhibited significant antioxidant activity in DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP assays. Its polysaccharide-rich nature, combined with antioxidant potential, suggests applications in food, nutraceutical, and therapeutic fields. These findings highlight the value of orange peel as a sustainable source of bioactive pectin.

REFERENCE

- Ahmad Jawad, T.A.G. Langrish (2012). Optimisation of total phenolic acids extraction from mandarin peels using microwave energy: the importance of the maillard reaction. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 109: 162–74.
- Bocco A., Marie-Elisabeth Cuvelier, Hubert Richard, Claudette Berset (1998). Antioxidant activity and phenolic composition of citrus peel and seed extracts. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 46: 2123–29.
- Bradford Marion M. (1976). ‘Rapid and sensitive method for the quantitation of microgram quantities of protein utilizing the principle of protein-dye binding. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 72: 248–54.
- Carmona Lourdes, Lorenzo Zacarias, María J. Rodrigo (2012). Stimulation of coloration and carotenoid biosynthesis during postharvest storage of ‘Navelina’ orange fruit at 12 C. *Postharvest Biology and Technology*, 74: 108–17.

- Cheftel J. Claude (1980). Introduction à la biochimie et à la technologie des aliments. Technique et Documentation: Enterprise Moderne.
- Chokri Souha, Sonia Ben Younes, Ali Ellafi, Sami Mnif, Eduardo Alberto López-Maldonado, Ahmed Slaheddine Masmoudi (2024). Exploring *Rhamnus alaternus* polysaccharides: Extraction, characterization, and analysis of antioxidant and antimicrobial properties. *Polymers*, 16: 3180.
- Cunniff P., D. Washington (1997). Official methods of analysis of AOAC international. *J. AOAC Int.*, 80: 127A.
- Da Rocha, Janaina Cardozo, José Antônio da Cunha Ponciano Gomes, Eliane D'Elia (2010). Corrosion inhibition of carbon steel in hydrochloric acid solution by fruit peel aqueous extracts. *Corrosion Science*, 52: 2341–48.
- Deluca G., M.A. Joslyn (1957). The recovery of pectin from orange peel extracts as aluminum pectinate. *Food Technology*, 11: 137–41.
- DuBois Michel., K.A. Gilles, J.K. Hamilton, P.A. Rebers, Fred Smith (1956). Colorimetric method for determination of sugars and related substances. *Analytical Chemistry*, 28: 350–56.
- Faravash Ram Sanati, Farzin Zokaee Ashtiani (2008). The influence of acid volume, ethanol-to-extract ratio and acid-washing time on the yield of pectic substances extraction from peach pomace. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 22: 196–202.
- Fisher Katie, Carol A. Phillips (2006). The effect of lemon, orange and bergamot essential oils and their components on the survival of *Campylobacter Jejuni*, *Escherichia Coli* O157, *Listeria Monocytogenes*, *Bacillus Cereus* and *Staphylococcus Aureus in Vitro* and in food systems. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 101: 1232–40.
- Gonzatto Mateus Pereira, Júlia Scherer Santos (2023). Introductory chapter: world citrus production and research. In Citrus Research-Horticultural and Human Health Aspects. *IntechOpen*.
- Gorinstein Shela, Milena Cvikrova, Ivana Machackova (2004). Characterization of antioxidant compounds in Jaffa sweets and white grapefruits. *Food Chemistry*, 84: 503–10.
- Herbstreith and Fox. n.d. 'Chances and Limits for the Use of Pectins as Emulsifier'. Herbstreith and Fox. Accessed 22 October 2025.
- Huang Yung-Sheng, Su-Chen Ho (2010). Polymethoxy flavones are responsible for the anti-inflammatory activity of citrus fruit peel. *Food Chemistry*, 119: 868–73.
- Kurz Christina, Reinhold Carle, Andreas Schieber (2008). Characterisation of cell wall polysaccharide profiles of apricots (*Prunus Armeniaca* L.), Peaches (*Prunus Persica* L.), and Pumpkins (*Cucurbita* Sp.) for the evaluation of fruit product authenticity. *Food Chemistry*, 106: 421–30.
- Legentil A., I. Guichard, B. Piffaut, J.P. Haluk (1995). Characterization of strawberry pectin extracted by chemical means. *LWT-Food Science and Technology*, 28: 569–76.
- Li Xiaomin, Yanru Tang, Zhexion Xuan, Yinghui Liu, Fang Luo. 2007. Study on the preparation of orange peel cellulose adsorbents and biosorption of Cd²⁺ from aqueous solution. *Separation and Purification Technology*, 55: 69–75.
- Ma Ya-Qin, Jian-Chu Chen, Dong-Hong Liu, Xing-Qian Ye (2009). Simultaneous extraction of phenolic compounds of citrus peel extracts: Effect of ultrasound. *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry*, 16: 57–62.
- Manderson K., M. Pinart, K.M. Tuohy (2005). *In vitro* determination of prebiotic properties of oligosaccharides derived from an orange juice manufacturing by-product stream. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 71: 8383–89.
- Ministère de l'Agriculture de Tunisie (2014). Rapport d'activité Annuel: 12-15. - Accessed 22 October 2025.
- Nishant Roopendra Kumar, Ankur Tyagi, Neelu Kumari. n.d. Fruit anatomy and morphology: understanding form and function. *Diverse Insights of Fruit Science*, 50. Accessed 22 October 2025.
- Nithish S., Ram Kumar, Laxmi Rawat, Nurin Afzia, Tabli Ghosh (2025). Extraction of pectin from assam lemon (citrus limon) peel and its use in preparation of low-fat mayonnaise. *Sustainable Food Technology*, 3: 1128–35.
- Pourbafrani Mohammad, Gergely Forgács, Ilona Sárvári Horváth, Claes Niklasson, Mohammad J. Taherzadeh (2010). Production of biofuels, limonene and pectin from citrus wastes. *Bioresource Technology*, 101: 4246–50.
- Price Martin L., Steve Van Scoyoc, Larry G. Butler (1978). A critical evaluation of the vanillin reaction as an assay for tannin in sorghum grain. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 26: 1214–18.
- Qiang Xu, Chao YongLie, Wan QianBing (2009). Health benefit application of functional oligosaccharides. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 77: 435–41.
- Ralet Marie-Christine, Juan Carlos Cabrera, Estelle Bonnin, Bernard Quémener, Pilar Hellin, Jean-François Thibault (2005). Mapping sugar beet pectin acetylation pattern. *Phytochemistry*, 66: 1832–43.
- Rana Richa, Neha Thakur, Gopal Singh (2023). Climate change and its impact on fruit production.
- Rejeb M.N., D. Laffray, P. Louguet (1993). Physiologie du caroubier (*Ceratonia Siliqua* L.) en Tunisie.
- Rouse A.H., P.G. Crandall (1978). Pectin content of lime and lemon peel as extracted by nitric acid. *Journal of Food Science*, 43: 72–73.
- Rtibi Kaïs, Slimen Selmi, Dhokra Grami (2017). Chemical constituents and pharmacological actions of carob pods and leaves (*Ceratonia Siliqua* L.) on the gastrointestinal tract: A review. *Biomedicine and Pharmacotherapy*, 93: 522–28.
- Rtibi Kaïs, Slimen Selmi, Mohammed-Amine Jabri (2016). Protective effect of *Ceratonia siliqua* L. against a dextran sulfate sodium-induced alterations in liver and kidney in rat. *Journal of Medicinal Food*, 19: 882–89.
- Seymour Graham B., J. Paul Knox (2002). Pectins and their manipulation.
- Siddhuraju Perumal (2006). The antioxidant activity and free radical-scavenging capacity of phenolics of raw and dry heated moth bean (*Vigna Aconitifolia*) (Jacq.) Marechal seed extracts. *Food Chemistry*, 99: 149–57.
- Singh Ambrish, V.K. Singh, M.A. Quraishi (2010). Effect of fruit extracts of some environmentally benign green corrosion inhibitors on corrosion of mild steel in hydrochloric acid solution. *Journal of Materials and Environmental Science*, 1: 162–74.
- Singleton VI (1999). Analysis of total phenols and other oxidation substrates and antioxidants by means of folin-ciocalteu reagent. *Methods in Enzymology*, 299: 152–78.
- Voragen Alphons G.J., W. Pilnik, Jean-Francois Thibault, Monique Axelos M.A.V., Catherine M.G.C. Renard (1995). Pectins. *Food Polysaccharides and Their Applications*, 67.
- Wang Xin, Quanru Chen, Xin Lü (2014). Pectin extracted from apple pomace and citrus peel by subcritical water. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 38: 129–37.
- Wang Xin, Xin Lü (2014). Characterization of pectic polysaccharides extracted from apple pomace by hot-compressed water. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 102: 174–84.
- Wang Yuan-Chuen, Yueh-Chueh Chuang, Yu-Hua Ku (2007). Quantitation of bioactive compounds in citrus fruits cultivated in Taiwan. *Food Chemistry*, 102: 1163–71.
- Wilkins Mark R., Wilbur W. Widmer, Karel Grohmann (2007). Simultaneous saccharification and fermentation of citrus peel waste by *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae* to produce ethanol. *Process Biochemistry*, 42: 1614–19.
- Yapo B.M., Christelle Robert, Isabelle Etienne, Bernard Wathelet, Michel Paquot (2007). Effect of extraction conditions on the yield, purity and surface properties of sugar beet pulp pectin extracts. *Food Chemistry*, 100: 1356–64.
- Yapo Beda Marcel, Kouassi Leonard Koffi (2006). Yellow passion fruit rinda potential source of low-methoxyl pectin. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 54: 2738–44.
- Yeoh S., Jtag Shi, T.A.G. Langrish (2008). Comparisons between different techniques for water-based extraction of pectin from orange peels. *Desalination*, 218: 229–37.
- Zhishen Jia, Tang Mengcheng, Wu Jianming (1999). The determination of flavonoid contents in mulberry and their scavenging effects on superoxide radicals. *Food Chemistry*, 64: 555–59.